

Working Paper

Co-knowledge generation with communities to enhance understanding the impact of Covid-19 on women living with, or at risk of acquiring, HIV in South Africa

Shakira Choonara¹, Erik Lamontagne^{2,3}, Hilton Humphries^{1,4}, Lara Lewis¹, Keabetswe Dikgale¹, Anna Yakusik³, Dianne Massawe⁵, Ntombenhle Mkhize⁶, Farai Mzungu⁷, and Quarraisha Abdool Karim^{1,4,8}

¹ Centre for the AIDS Programme of Research in South Africa (CAPRISA), Nelson R Mandela School of Medicine, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa

² UNAIDS, Strategic Information, Geneva, Switzerland

³ Aix Marseille University, CNRS, Aix-Marseille School of Economics, Marseille, France.

⁴ Department of Psychology, School of Applied Human Sciences, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban, South Africa.

⁵ African Alliance, Johannesburg, South Africa

⁶ AIDS Foundation of South Africa, Durban, South Africa

⁷ Youth Health Africa, Johannesburg, South Africa.

⁸ Mailman School of Public Health, Columbia University, New York

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19667509>, UNAIDS, May 2023. South Africa.

Abstract

In Eastern and Southern Africa, home to about 60% of people living with HIV and new HIV infections, adolescent girls and young women (AGYW) continue to bear a disproportionate burden of new HIV infections and AIDS related mortality rates. AGYW and women living with HIV are diverse in terms of age, risk factors and geo-spatial distribution and are challenging to reach. The Covid-19 pandemic and the national measures to limit the propagation of the virus have revealed and exacerbated vulnerabilities AGYW in Africa are confronted with. The pandemic has had a wide range of health, social and economic impacts among this population group. There is growing evidence that these multi-dimensional impacts of Covid-19 are worse for key and vulnerable AGYW1-3.

This paper discusses how co-knowledge generation and partnerships established with civil society organisations, enabled us to effectively and efficiently reach diverse communities of marginalised women in South Africa, enhance the quality and completeness of data collected online and through peer interviews, strengthened community capacity to undertake research, and rapidly utilise the information generated to institute or advocate for interventions to mitigate a deepening crisis of HIV, TB gender and poverty.

Summary/ Key Messages

- Covid-19 is unmasking profound socio-economic impacts in South Africa, although the impact of Covid-19 on already vulnerable populations women and girls living with HIV and at high risk of HIV such as is less understood.
- The needs of this diverse population of women are met partially by traditional health service centres and mostly by a range of civil society organisations in South Africa.
- Establishing strong partnerships enabled us to reach the target populations to implement the study (national cross-sectional survey).
- Co-knowledge generation from conception, optimising the survey questionnaire, peer data collection and data analysis and interpretation enabled this survey to be undertaken in the midst of a Covid-19 surge in South Africa.

Introduction

HIV remains a global health crisis. With an estimated 1.5 million new HIV infections and 680 000 AIDS related deaths in 2021 (UNAIDS, 2021 – UNAIDS Data), the world is not on track to achieve the United Nations General Assembly Political Declaration – to end AIDS as a public health threat by 2030. Eastern and Southern Africa bears a disproportionate 55 percent of the global burden of HIV infection, with 58% of infections in adolescent girls and young women (UNAIDS, 2021). In this region, South Africa is home to 20 percent of the global burden of HIV infections, translating to an overall prevalence of 24.7% or an estimated 8 million people living with HIV (UNAIDS, 2021). In South Africa, ... (data on SA).

The Covid-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on health of nations globally reducing life expectancy and disrupting other essential health services including sexual reproductive health services, HIV prevention and treatment services, services and maternal and child health services (ref). In addition, Covid-19 has had substantial socio-economic impacts with already marginalized and vulnerable populations bearing a disproportionate burden of its multiple impacts. Women are bearing a disproportionate burden of rising levels of gender-based violence, unplanned pregnancies, household and parenting responsibilities and loss of jobs. (UNAIDS, 2020 – COVID-19 and HIV). The long term impact of Covid-19 on adolescent girls and young women living with, or at high risk of acquiring HIV in sub-Saharan Africa is not known.

The Centre for the AIDS Programme of Research in South Africa (CAPRISA), a UNAIDS Collaborating Centre for Research and Policy with support from UNAIDS Geneva aimed to quantify and describe the impacts of the Covid-19 pandemic on women and girls living with HIV or at high risk of acquiring HIV in South Africa. This paper discusses how co-knowledge generation partnerships established with civil society organisations, enabled the scientific community and civil society and community-based organisations to effectively and efficiently reach diverse communities of marginalised women in South Africa, enhance the quality and completeness of data collected online and through peer interviews, strengthened community

capacity to undertake research, potentially enable a more complete representativity with under-the-radar vulnerable and highly stigmatised AGYW, and rapidly utilise the information generated to institute or advocate for interventions to mitigate a deepening crisis of HIV, TB gender and poverty.

Overview of the survey

This cross-sectional survey was undertaken between August 2021 and November 2021 in four provinces with the highest HIV and Covid-19 burden in SA namely; the Eastern Cape, Gauteng, KwaZulu Natal and the Western Cape (Humphries et al, 2022). Purposive sampling was used to enrol 2280, 15-64 year old women and girls living with HIV or at high risk of acquiring HIV infection. The sample included women from key and vulnerable populations including adolescent girls and young women; sex workers, LGBTQ+ women, women on the move and women using recreational drugs. The emphasis in sampling was less on representativeness but more on ensuring the diversity of women living with HIV or at high risk of acquiring HIV were included particularly where there was also a high burden of Covid-19. Sex work and substance use (except marijuana use) is criminalised in South Africa. While the constitution protects the rights of the LGBTQ+ community there is substantial social stigma as with people living with HIV and sexually active adolescent girls. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire built from validated instruments and questions from civil society and community-based organisations that included items on: Covid-19 epidemic and sanitary measures -such as lockdown-, socio-economic vulnerability, behaviours, macrosocial determinants, health and well-being, gender-based violence, substance use, transactional sex and sex work. The survey was translated into the two common indigenous languages used in the 4 provinces - Xhosa and isiZulu. Questionnaires were either self-administered on paper or online or completed through interviewer facilitation following informed consent. Participants were re-imbursed approximately \$3 for completing the questionnaire (Humphries et al, 2022). The study protocol was approved by University of KwaZulu-Natal Biomedical Research Ethics Committee (BREC, 00002727/2021). To understand the full impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on women and girls living with HIV and to reach these communities, multi-stakeholder partnerships were imperative in being able to reach hard-to-reach populations.

Study context: Covid-19 and political unrest

The SA national response to Covid-19 included declaring a national state of disaster on March 27, 2020, restricted international travel, school closures, limited public gatherings and a mandatory daily curfew between 9.00 pm and 5.00 am daily, to slow down the spread of Covid-19 (Baxter et al, 2019). At the individual level, measures such as wearing masks, sanitising hands frequently and physical distancing was instituted. The levels of restrictions of movement and curfews were based on the number of Covid-19 cases reported, i.e. stricter measures were in place during the approximately three monthly surges of infection due to emerging variants of concern. In addition to the ongoing surges of SARS-CoV-2 infections there was a political insurrection in July 2021, KwaZulu Natal and to a limited extent in Gauteng and the Eastern Cape resulting in additional challenges for vulnerable population groups for almost six months.

The onset of the Covid-19 pandemic in early 2020 was mitigated through public health measures such as strict lockdowns restricting movement within countries, outside of borders and public health gatherings. The Covid-19 pandemic and mitigation measures while necessary hampered our ability to reach vulnerable communities such as women and girls living with HIV.

Process in preparation for survey implementation

Prior to commencing the project, consultations were held with established CSOs with a track record of providing HIV services to adolescent girls and young women, sex workers, women on the move, lesbian/ transgender populations about the planned survey and purpose. CSOs and CBOs in South Africa are diverse and connected to communities, understand contextual sensitivities and are able to navigate the sensitivities of conducting research among key and vulnerable populations including women and girls living with HIV. The involvement of these organisations at all stages of the survey was important to reaching target populations in the circumstances described above. Additional benefits included a more relevant, and likely more useful, questionnaire, an innovative sharing of knowledge involving academic approach and on-the-ground reality, , gather CSO insights to simplify the survey for communities.

Community engagement, capacity development and key partnerships were central to undertaking this national-level cross sectional survey. At the project planning stage, a comprehensive mapping was carried out, focusing on key CSOs engaged in HIV service provision, especially those involved in service provision to key and vulnerable populations. Briefing sessions were held with these organizations before survey initiation. Interest in partnering to conduct of the survey was explored. An open call for grant applications was shared with all CSOs. All grant applications received were reviewed and ranked based on pre-set criteria that included a track record of service provision and outreach to key and vulnerable populations identified for inclusion in the survey; projected budgets, timelines, and inclusion of training and capacity development plans for data collectors and staff working on the survey. Three CSO partnerships were established with the AIDS Foundation of South Africa (AFSA), African Alliance (AA), and Youth Health Africa (YHA). During the data collection process, two gaps were identified, namely; limited reach of migrant and displaced populations and injecting drug users. To address this gap, additional/ purposeful support was sought from CSOs, the Denis Hurley Centre and TB/HIV Care, respectively.

CSOs advised that in order to reach at risk populations; adolescent girls and young women, sex workers, migrants, lesbian and transgender populations there would be a need for face-to-face (assisted data collection). Primary reasons for the need to conduct face-to-face data collection was due to the complex types of questions, the varying levels of literacy, sensitivity of topics being explored such as gender-based violence, or openly disclosing one's HIV status which would require counselling and referrals, dire socio-economic conditions means that participants lack data/ are unable to meet the costs of data and the lack up-to-date technology to complete a 20-30 minute online survey.

The pandemic altered how survey data is collected to protect the health and safety of those conducting surveys and stop potential disease transmission (Phadnis et al, 2019). There was a need to navigate this challenging context and to be able to collect data among hard-to-reach populations/ communities without exposing both the CSO and the participants to the COVID-19. Several research studies transitioned to being fully online or making use of tele-methods during the Covid-19 pandemic. However, in the South African context, the intended target population (women and girls living with HIV including key and vulnerable populations) could not be reached solely through online platforms. Strong and equal partnerships with CSOs who have the necessary experience and networks proved to be critical and valuable in collecting data and reaching at-risk and vulnerable populations.

Survey joint implementation & co-knowledge generation with civil society organisations

Each CSO brought a unique added advantage based on respective strengths and strongly complemented each other. The AIDS Foundation of South Africa is involved with a great network of adolescent girls and young women through its HIV programmes across the country as well as with multiple key and vulnerable population programming. The AIDS Foundation of South Africa aided in reaching adolescent girls and young women despite school closures as a result of Covid-19 through innovative approaches. The AIDS Foundation of South Africa, with their wealth of experience and interventions on gender-based violence and HIV disclosure components, lead the related sections of the survey which were extremely sensitive, possibly triggering and provided counselling and referrals where necessary for participants.

The African Alliance, is a leading CSO which prioritises advocacy for key and vulnerable populations. The African Alliance tapped into existing networks, recruited data collectors from key and vulnerable populations, facilitated skills transfer and research capacity development, ensured inclusion of diverse populations and navigating legally sensitive contexts such as reaching female sex workers in brothels or people who inject drugs or migrant populations. The African Alliance, established a partnership with community-based organizations to identify peer recruiters and data collectors as well as ensured that the project reached key and vulnerable populations e.g. sex workers and the LGBTIQ+ community in South Africa.

The country currently grapples high levels of unemployment among young people - the unemployment rate for youth aged 15-24 years is 63,9% and 42,1% for youth aged 25-34 years (<https://www.statssa.gov.za/?p=15407>). The third partner, Youth Health Africa took the lead on training and providing skills and employment opportunities for 200 unemployed youth. Youth Health Africa took the lead in developing comprehensive training materials and training data collectors on Covid-19 protocols e.g. maintaining physical distancing, sanitising hands and equipment (ipads/ mobile phones). Personal protective equipment (PPE) was also provided for both data collectors and participants to reduce any risks of SARS-CoV-2 transmission.

Reaching injecting drug users and migrants remained a challenge and this gap was filled by reaching out to organisations in KwaZulu-Natal who were dedicated service providers to these marginalised populations - the Dennis Hurley Centre provides AIDS treatment services to

asylum seekers and undocumented migrants and the Bellhaven Centre is a supervised substance use centre supported by another local NGO.

Once the raw quantitative data was analysed, project partners worked together to identify key emerging themes and civil society partners worked closely together with researchers to co-produce peer-reviewed publications, present at conferences, holding virtual multi-stakeholder dissemination meetings. Partners have already jointly published initial study findings on the “Impact of COVID-19 public health responses on income, food security and health services among key and vulnerable women in South Africa”. This manuscript is another example of ongoing collaboration and knowledge co-generation essential to addressing the impacts of the covid-19 pandemic and effectively engaging CSOs and communities.

Conclusion

This study and its approach demonstrates the value of co-knowledge generation to reach communities being missed in traditional HIV, broader health and pandemic responses. In this era of increasing new and emerging pandemics that underscore our interconnectedness and shared vulnerability as a global community, enhancing resilience is a key component of better pandemic preparedness. The UN sustainable development framework and goals remain an important instrument for ensuring no one is left behind. Notably Sustainable Development Goal 17 highlights the importance of strong global partnerships and cooperation (United Nations. N.d). at global, regional, national and local levels that are built on a shared vision and benefitting from placing people at the centre (United Nations. N.d). The global movement to ‘End AIDS’ has shown us that communities must be front and centre of health responses, interventions must be tailored to the local context, there must be strong social trust and community buy-in (UNAIDS, 2020 – COVID-19 and HIV). The implications of community resistance, mistrust of governments, health systems, fear, stigma and misinformation were shown to hinder efforts to tackle Ebola (UNAIDS, 2020 – COVID-19 and HIV). Similarly, during the Covid-19 pandemic, the rise of misinformation, vaccine hesitancy and stigma were also on the increase. Civil society remains a key stakeholder in reaching and placing people at the centre of the HIV response and in addressing other new and emerging crises that render some populations more vulnerable to others or where new crises exacerbate the vulnerability of already marginalised or stigmatised or discriminated communities.

The study shows that CSOs continue to be best placed in reaching communities even during challenging times. Equal and multi-stakeholder partnerships (UNAIDS, CAPRISA, AIDS Foundation of South Africa, African Alliance, Youth Health Africa and the Dennis Hurley Centre) allowed for implementation of this project and enrolling 2280 women and girls living with HIV or at high risk of acquiring HIV during the Covid-19 pandemic in South Africa.

CSOs were able to reach the most marginalised populations e.g. migrant communities, adolescent girls and sex workers despite lockdowns and other Covid-19 mitigation measures.

Contributions were made to capacity development; training and employment of peer data collectors from key and vulnerable populations and the employment and skills development of 200 youth data collectors. The benefit of multi-stakeholder partnerships is anticipated to lead to evidence-based advocacy, and programming and ensuring a synergistic and trusted response to the ongoing HIV and gender crisis as well as new challenges such as Covid-19.

Lessons learnt

- This study confirms that civil society organisations are able to reach marginalised populations as they are trusted and have a profound understanding of the multiple structural, social and economic factors that intersect and underpin their vulnerability.
- Co-knowledge generation is possible even during a pandemic crisis. Respectful and trusted partnerships require engagement as early as possible at the conceptual stage and continue throughout the project including in interpretation of data and conclusions drawn. Community organisations provide granular and nuanced insights on context and sensitives, in translating documents to a local language or in reaching a marginalised population such as the LGBTQTI+ community or sex workers, or the timing of interviews at safe or convenient times and ensuring privacy for survey completion. Multi-stakeholder partnerships are valuable in generating meaningful evidence and ensuring the utilisation for evidence-informed advocacy and programming.
- There are opportunities in undertaking research to build capacity and create employment opportunities e.g. recruitment and training of peer data collectors from key and vulnerable populations or unemployed youth.
- Opportunities to mitigate risk during the research process. Inclusion of Covid-19 risk mitigation training and provision of hand sanitisers and masks for both data collectors and participants.
- While virtual platforms have enabled connections and continuity for some stakeholders and populations, access varies within and between communities. As we invest in enhancing resilience of communities and countries we need to ensure equitable access to technologies and also ensure skills in use of the technology is even. In the interim, hybrid approaches are key for inclusivity and more balanced representation of all populations.
- The Covid-19 pandemic has led to a diminishing funding landscape, CSOs have been severely impacted, this study draws attention to the importance and value of investing in and partnering with CSOs, multi-fold benefits include service delivery, reaching communities, knowledge co-generation and advocacy.

Conflict of interest

References

1. Humphries H, Lewis L, Lamontagne E, et al. Impact of COVID-19 public health responses on income, food security and health services among key and vulnerable women in South Africa. *African Journal of AIDS Research* 2022; **21**(4): 317-29.
2. Lamontagne E, Folayan MO, Arije O, et al. The effects of COVID-19 on food insecurity, financial vulnerability and housing insecurity among women and girls living with or at risk of HIV in Nigeria. *African Journal of AIDS Research* 2022: 1-9.
3. Folayan MO, Arije O, Enemo A, et al. Factors associated with poor access to HIV and sexual and reproductive health services in Nigeria for women and girls living with HIV during the COVID-19 pandemic. *African Journal of AIDS Research* 2022; **21**(2): 171-82.

DRAFT